

Simulation of jet installation effects at Mach=0.9: influence of numerical methodology and physical insights

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The noise radiated by an isothermal, single-stream jet with a Mach number $M=0.9$ and diameter-based Reynolds number $Re_D = 10^6$ is investigated numerically without and with the presence of a flat plate. Noise sources are predicted with Zonal Detached Eddy Simulations mode 3 together with turbulence tripping inside the nozzle to recover an initially turbulent flow, while radiated pressure is extrapolated with integral methods. Numerical methodology, namely grid and statistical convergence of the signals, is assessed for the isolated jet. Noise levels are accurately simulated at least up to $St = 8$ and integrated pressure levels collapse within 1 dB with the experiments. In the presence of the plate, an innovative noise radiation methodology based on integral methods is proposed to reconstruct the pressure signals at microphone locations with a reduced numerical cost. The simulation compares very favorably with the experimental data, azimuthal noise variations induced by the plate are correctly captured and noise levels collapse within 1 dB. It is concluded the numerical methodology is mature enough for application in an industrial context.

1 Introduction

Among all the noise sources of an aircraft, jet noise remains a dominant one and still requires a lot of attention. For an isolated jet the acoustic power follows the well-known Lighthill's power law, which predicts a variation of the power with the eighth power of the flow velocity [1]. Jet noise is therefore particularly strong during take-off, where a high power setting of the engine is required and results in a transonic, highly turbulent jet flow. The interested reader may refer to the reviews of Bailly and Kaji [2] and Tam [3] for details on isolated jet noise sources. During the last decades, important jet noise reduction has been achieved by decreasing the jet velocity, first through the use of double stream nozzles, then by the increase of the bypass ratio of the engine, and therefore an increase of its size. When the engine is positioned close to the wing, the turbulent flow generates additional low-frequency noise known as installed jet noise or jet-surface interaction (JSI) noise [4]. For recent engines, the bypass ratio rises above 15 and leads to integration problem [5] [6] which increases the contribution of installed jet noise.

Jet installation noise has been widely investigated experimentally over the years for both simplified [4] [7] [8] [9] [10] and more realistic, industrial-like configurations [11] [12] [13]. Among others, Lawrence et al. performed an extensive experimental campaign for various axial and radial distances between the jet and the trailing edge of the plate as well as jet Mach number [8]. Results particularly evidence the sensitivity of noise production to the trailing edge position and the predominance of JSI noise for low velocity jets. Finally, by comparing jet installation noise issued from a flat plate or

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realistic wings, Lawrence experimentally found that jet data scale well between both configurations so that the jet-plate configuration is well suited for analytical, numerical and experimental investigations [14].

From a theoretical point of view, Ffowcs Williams and Hall proved low-frequency noise is increased when flow turbulence is scattered by the trailing edge of the solid surface and radiates predominantly in the upstream direction [15]. This scattered noise scales with the fifth power of the flow velocity, which makes it dominant compared to the free-jet noise for low Mach numbers. Cavalieri et al. observed the scattered sound decreases exponentially with the increasing jet-plate distance and suggested it is produced by the scattering of evanescent hydrodynamic wavepackets in the jet [7]. The identification of turbulence scattering as the main mechanism of installed jet noise paved the way to analytical modelling of JSI noise [7] [10] [16] [17] [18] [19] [20]. It is worth noting that, except when the plate is very close to the jet, the wavepacket structure is barely impacted by the presence of the solid surface and isolated jet data may be used to model installation noise, which results in a drastic reduction of the numerical/experimental effort to characterize the source [7].

There are numerous examples of jet aeroacoustics simulation in the literature [21] [22] [23] [24] [25] [26] [27]. Despite the rapid increase of computational power, the cost of Direct Numerical Simulation (DNS) still remains prohibitive for large scale or complex configurations. For large Reynolds number jet flows, Large Eddy Simulation (LES) represents a good option because it allows the resolution of large scale turbulent structures, responsible of turbulent energy production, and therefore noise generation, whereas small-scale turbulence is assumed to be isotropic and is modelled. The capacity of flow resolution inside the jet plume is nevertheless not sufficient by itself to accurately predict jet noise, as flow development is also driven by the state of the shear layer at nozzle exit, either laminar for low Reynolds number or turbulent for larger values. This phenomenon has been evidenced experimentally by Zaman [28] [29] and numerically by Bogey et al. [30] [31] for instance. Initially laminar jets exhibit an additional noise source in the medium frequency range due to vortex pairings in the shear layer, that remain present for high Reynolds number jet if no turbulence is seeded in the boundary layer. Several solutions are available to trigger this boundary layer turbulence, such as the injection of small random velocity disturbances [30] [31] [32], a turbulence rescaling-recycling procedure [33] or various synthetic turbulence methods [34] [35] [36] [37]. In order to reduce the acoustic perturbations which can be generated by synthetic methods and mimic the experimental turbulence triggering devices, geometrical forcing can be considered [38] [39]. Of interest, Deck et al. [40] have proposed a method based on roughness elements –or tripping dots– included in the computational domain with the Immersed Boundary Condition (IBC) [41] to trigger turbulent transition mechanisms resolved with a Wall Modelled LES (WMLES) approach, namely the mode 3 of Zonal Detached Eddy Simulation (ZDES) [42] [43]. This approach was successfully applied to jet flows in [44] and the method appeared well suited for aeroacoustics applications.

Acoustic waves can be propagated to microphones locations in the CFD simulation, but this approach is unnecessarily expensive. Viscous and turbulent flow effects being negligible during propagation, which occurs essentially in uniform mean flows, a two-step procedure is classically employed where noise radiation is achieved as a post-processing with Computational AeroAcoustics (CAA) simulation [45] [46] or with the help of integral methods [47] [48]. The Ffowcs Williams and Hawkings (FWH) integral method [49] is particularly well suited for turbulent flows and is commonly used for isolated jets [48] [50] [51]. With this approach the far-field pressure fluctuations are reconstructed from the unsteady flow fields on a porous surface encompassing the noise sources for a very affordable numerical cost. This methodology remains valid in the presence of a wing and has been used by several authors [6] [52] [53] [54] [55] [56] [57] [58]. The numerical cost of the CFD simulation

however becomes important when the wing span is large because all acoustic effects, including the propagation of acoustic waves up to the wing extremities, need to be accurately captured during the flow simulation. To address this issue, some authors couple the CFD simulation, dedicated to the production of noise and its propagation in the close vicinity of the jet and wing, with a CAA simulation that propagates noise around the wing towards a uniform mean flow where an integral method is used for the radiation to the far-field microphones [50] [59]. CAA simulations being cheaper than CFD ones for the propagation of acoustic waves with the same order of accuracy, this approach is expected to limit the total computational cost. It nevertheless requires the construction of a dedicated numerical grid for the CAA simulation and some engineering and numerical efforts to run the simulations. In the present study, an alternative procedure is applied for the first time on installed jet configurations using integral methods. Similarly to the isolated configuration, a porous surface is located in the vicinity of the jet plume to limit the computational cost of the CFD. Jet-plate interactions occurring inside the surface are captured by CFD and are taken into account in the noise radiated to the far-field through their contribution in the perturbation field on the porous surface whereas acoustic reflections on the flat plate outside the storage surface are modelled in the radiation process: the flat plate is represented as a solid surface in the noise simulation and the contribution of the reflections to the total radiated noise is computed with an integral method.

The article is organized as follows. The numerical methodologies for the reproduction of initially turbulent jet flows and their noise radiation with integral methods are detailed in Section 2. The isolated and installed jet test cases, corresponding to an isothermal, Mach 0.9 turbulent jet, are described in Section 3 together with the numerical settings for the simulations. Aerodynamic and acoustic assessment of the isolated simulation are provided in Section 4, together with an evaluation of the convergence of the statistical data. The installed jet is simulated in Section 5. The new radiation method for jet-wing configuration is presented and validated against CFD results before flow and noise changes caused by the presence of the plate are discussed. To end, conclusions are drawn in Section 6.

2 Computational methodologies

2.1 Zonal Detached Eddy Simulation

The hybrid RANS/LES method used in this work is the Zonal Detached Eddy Simulation (ZDES) [42] developed at ONERA. This approach has been used with success to simulate a wide range of applications of industrial interest [60]. One of the advantages of the ZDES is that it covers several types of detached flows, which can be combined. It is important to bear in mind that modes 1 and 2 of ZDES belong to the so-called “natural Detached Eddy Simulation” approaches in which the attached boundary layers are treated in RANS. Conversely, mode 3 of ZDES is a Wall Modelled LES approach in which the outer part of attached boundary layers is resolved in LES. An example of the combined use of the three modes of ZDES within the same computation can be found in Ref [61]. Since most of the work presented in this article relies on ZDES mode 3, only this operating mode formulation is presented below. The reader is referred to [42] [44] [60] for detailed descriptions of the ZDES equations.

The ZDES is based on the basic idea of the original Detached Eddy Simulation [62] (DES97) which relies on the Spalart-Allmaras (SA) RANS model [63]. A brief description of the SA model is provided below, the reader is referred to the original paper [63] for a full description. The SA model is based on the transport equation of a pseudo viscosity $\tilde{\nu}$ involving production, diffusion and destruction terms:

$$\frac{D\tilde{\nu}}{Dt} = \underbrace{c_{b1}\tilde{S}\tilde{\nu}}_{production} + \underbrace{\frac{1}{\sigma}[\nabla \cdot ((\nu + \tilde{\nu})\nabla\tilde{\nu}) + c_{b2}(\nabla\tilde{\nu})^2]}_{diffusion} - \underbrace{c_{w1}f_w \left[\frac{\tilde{\nu}}{d_w} \right]^2}_{destruction} \quad (1)$$

where d_w is the distance to the wall, c_{b1} , c_{b2} and c_{w1} are constants, \tilde{S} is a modified vorticity magnitude involving a near wall function f_{v2} and f_w is another near-wall function. The eddy viscosity entering the Boussinesq closure for the RANS equations is defined using a third near-wall function f_{v1} : $\nu_t = f_{v1}\tilde{\nu}$. The three near-wall corrections f_w , f_{v1} and f_{v2} were calibrated to ensure the correct behavior of $\tilde{\nu}$ in the viscous, buffer, log-layer and outer parts of the boundary layer. The basic principle of DES97 is to modify the destruction term of eq. (1) so that the RANS eddy-viscosity is reduced to a LES subgrid scale one in detached areas. To do so, the distance to the wall in eq. (1) is replaced by $\check{d}_{DES97} = \min(d_w, C_{DES}\Delta)$ with $C_{DES}=0.65$ and $\Delta=\Delta_{max}$ is the maximum cell size. With this modification, away from the walls, when production and destruction terms are balanced, the eddy viscosity scales with the local mesh size and the local vorticity modulus: $\nu_t \approx S\Delta^2$ which is similar to Smagorinsky's subgrid scale model.

Therefore the transport equation for ZDES reads:

$$\frac{D\tilde{\nu}}{Dt} = \underbrace{c_{b1}\tilde{S}\tilde{\nu}}_{production} + \underbrace{\frac{1}{\sigma}[\nabla \cdot ((\nu + \tilde{\nu})\nabla\tilde{\nu}) + c_{b2}(\nabla\tilde{\nu})^2]}_{diffusion} - \underbrace{c_{w1}f_w \left[\frac{\tilde{\nu}}{\check{d}_{ZDES}} \right]^2}_{destruction} \quad (2)$$

The hybrid length scale \check{d}_{ZDES} is defined for each mode 1, 2 and 3, see [42]. The present work focuses on the use of ZDES mode 3 which formulation is detailed in the following.

The mode 3 of ZDES was defined to act as a Wall Modelled LES in attached boundary layers. Let us be reminded that within WMLES, turbulence in the outer-layer is LES-resolved whereas a near-wall RANS zone plays the role of wall model. Therefore the definition of the hybrid length scale \check{d}_{ZDES}^{III} relies on the specification of a RANS/LES interface height $d_w^{interface}$ within the boundary layer according to eq. (3):

$$\check{d}_{ZDES}^{III} = \begin{cases} d_w \text{ if } d_w < d_w^{interface}(x) \\ \min \left(\frac{d_w}{\check{d}_{RANS}}, \frac{C_{DES}\Delta_{ZDES}^I}{\check{d}_{LES}} \right) \text{ otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

In the present study, the value $d_w^{interface}(x) = 0.1 \delta(x)$ was chosen. $\delta(x)$ is the local boundary layer thickness and is determined by a precursor RANS calculation. See Refs [43] [64] for further discussion of the interface location. ZDES mode 3 was used and validated for WMLES in [55] [61] [64] [65].

In order to perform WMLES simulations of fully turbulent boundary layers, resolved turbulence must be injected into the incoming flow in order to initiate the resolved turbulence development. This means that the ZDES mode 3 technique has to be used in association with a turbulent injection method such as the one discussed in the following section.

2.2 Turbulence generation using immersed boundary condition

Instead of using a body-fitted grid to account for wall boundaries, the basic idea of the IBC method is to mark the solid and fluid zones of the computational mesh and to take into account the wall presence by adding a source term in the Navier Stokes equations in order to mimic a solid boundary.

The formulation of the IBC method used in this study is identical to the one detailed in [40], which was first proposed in [41] and was inspired by the direct forcing approach of [66] [67] adapted to curvilinear grids and RANS/LES methods. The source term entering the Navier-Stokes equations for the IBC forcing is defined so that the momentum and pseudo eddy viscosity transport equations return to zero, thus acting as a solid boundary. The roughness elements are introduced in order to produce streamwise vorticity in the boundary layer at the location where it is most likely to be amplified and thus generate resolved turbulence to initiate the WMLES behavior of ZDES mode 3. The most suited shape parameters of the roughness elements were identified in [40] using a parametric study. Note that in [40], the authors also used the Dynamic Forcing method (DF) [68] to accelerate the development of three-dimensional turbulence downstream of the roughness elements. This method was not used in the present work since the length of the nozzle duct is large enough for the turbulence generated by the tripping dots to develop at an affordable CPU cost without the need of DF (see section 4.2).

2.3 Noise radiation

To limit the computational cost of the simulation, the unsteady flow is resolved only in the flow region containing the noise sources, and the pressure radiated outside this region is calculated using surface integral methods.

For the isolated jet configuration, the pressure radiated at the observer location \vec{x} can be calculated in the time domain using one of the two following formulas developed at ONERA from the FWH surface formulation (see details and notations in [69] [70]).

$$p'(\vec{x}, t) = \iint_{\tau S} \left(F_{FWH} + \frac{\partial F'_{FWH}}{\partial \tau} \right) G dS d\tau \quad (4)$$

$$p'(\vec{x}, t) = \iint_{\tau S} F_{FWH}(\vec{x}, \vec{y}, \tau) G dS d\tau + \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \iint_{\tau S} F'_{FWH}(\vec{x}, \vec{y}, \tau) G dS d\tau \quad (5)$$

where $F_{FWH} = \frac{\beta^2}{d^2} \Sigma_1$, $F'_{FWH} = \frac{\Sigma_1}{a_0 d} + \frac{\Sigma_2}{\beta^2}$, $\Sigma_1 = \left(A_i(x_i - y_i) + \frac{(M_0^2 A_1 - U_0 B)}{\beta^2} (x_1 - y_1) \right)$,

$\Sigma_2 = B - \frac{M_0 A_1}{a_0}$, $G = \frac{\delta(g)}{4\pi d}$, A_i and B depending only on the aerodynamic field on the integration surface S .

Formula (4) is limited to fixed integration surfaces but has the advantage of minimizing the acoustic calculation self-noise. The time derivative outside the integration in formula (5) tends to amplify the numerical noise of the acoustic calculation at its frequency sampling and a few sub-harmonics, but significantly simplifies the expression of additional terms (not present in formula (4)) that have been developed for integration surfaces crossed by turbulent flows [70]. These additional terms allow the use of such surfaces while avoiding spurious noise generated by turbulence [48]. For jet noise computations, the use of closed integration surfaces (as the FWH formulation theoretically requires), together with these additional surface terms, improve in particular the acoustic predictions in the low-frequency part of the spectra [70]. Therefore, the acoustic calculations presented in this study are carried out using expression (5) supplemented by these additional terms.

For the installed jet configuration, a complementary acoustic calculation is performed to take into account the presence of the plate in the sound radiation (see Section 5.2.1). This second calculation is carried out using the Kirchhoff method using the following classic formula for a fixed integration surface S [69]:

$$p'(\bar{x}, t) = \int_{\tau} \int_S F_K(\bar{x}, \bar{y}, \tau) G dS d\tau \quad (6)$$

$$\text{where } F_K = \beta^2 \frac{(x_i - y_i) n_i}{d^2} p'_{ref} - \frac{\partial p'_{ref}}{\partial y_i} n_i + M_0^2 n_1 \frac{\partial p'_{ref}}{\partial y_1} + \frac{1}{a_0} \left(\frac{(x_i - y_i) n_i}{d} + M_0 n_1 \right) \frac{\partial p'_{ref}}{\partial \tau}.$$

In the expression of F_K , p'_{ref} is the reflected pressure on the plate. This reflected pressure is simply determined as a function of the incident pressure, its gradient, its time derivative (these quantities being provided by the first calculation), the local normal to the surface, and the observer location. The method is described in detail in [71]. The model is based on the hypothesis of locally planar reflections but predicts reflection and shadow effects of curved surfaces fairly well (see example in Figure 1). On the other hand, because of this hypothesis of small wavelength with respect to the reflecting surface local curvature, this approach only partially predicts diffraction effects (this is why in the present study the trailing edge of the plate is enclosed as much as possible in FWH porous surface). This approach assumes a uniform mean flow and thus does not account for refraction effects.

(a) Kirchhoff method

(b) Euler simulation

Figure 1. Pressure field produced by a point source in the vicinity of a NACA 0012 profile (flow Mach number 0.5)

For both formulations, the time derivatives are calculated by second-order centered finite differences. The computations are carried out starting from the emission times τ_j and the pressures at the prescribed reception times t_k are calculated by linear interpolations of the pressures obtained at the reception times $t_j = \tau_j + \sigma/c_0$ and $t_{j+1} = \tau_{j+1} + \sigma/c_0$ on either side of time t_k (σ being the acoustic distance and c_0 the sound velocity in the propagation medium). The time integration scheme is thus also of second order.

3 Test cases and simulation setup

3.1 Isolated and installed jet test cases

The jet configuration investigated in this report is a single stream, subsonic, isothermal jet from Pprime laboratory in Poitiers, France [37]. The exhaust Mach number is equal to $M=0.9$, the nozzle exit diameter is $D = 0.05$ m, the nozzle pressure ratio is $P_i/P_0 = 1.7$ and the nozzle temperature ratio is $T_i/T_0 = 1.15$. The Reynolds number based on the diameter is equal to $Re_D = 10^6$ and the boundary layer inside the nozzle is tripped, so that the flow is fully turbulent. All isolated experimental data and nozzle geometry are available online [37]. For the installed jet case illustrated in Figure 2, it is chosen to locate the plate at its closest radial position with respect to the nozzle, $0.6D$. The distance from the nozzle exit to the plate trailing edge is $4D$ and the wing span is $15D$. The experimental setup is detailed in [9].

Figure 2. Jet/plate installation setup

Acoustic levels are analyzed on the experimental, azimuthal antenna of 18 evenly distributed microphones of Pprime [9]. The circular antenna is centered on the jet axis with a radius of $14.3D$ and is moved axially from $x/D=39.29$ to $x/D=-8.26$ ($x/D=-1.25$ experimentally), corresponding to observation angles θ varying from 20° to 120° (resp. 95°) with a 5° step, as illustrated in Figure 3. For the installed case, pressure levels are expected to depend on the azimuthal angle of the microphones Φ , whose definition is illustrated in Figure 3. (b). It is measured counterclockwise with respect to the positive x axis. $\Phi = 0^\circ$ is aligned with the positive z axis, so that angles $0^\circ \leq \Phi \leq 180^\circ$ correspond to positions above the flat plate (shielded side) whereas angles $180^\circ \leq \Phi \leq 360^\circ$ are located below the plate (unshielded side). Finally, power spectral densities and integrated levels follow the $1/M_j^4$ scaling proposed by Brès et al. (see Eq. B 8 of [37]) and the frequency range considered for the integrated levels is $0.05 \leq St \leq 10$.

Figure 3. (a) Microphones positions for the different locations of the azimuthal antenna, (b) azimuthal description of the microphones on the antenna

3.2 Numerical settings

The computational domain used is the same for all simulations and is illustrated for the isolated case in Figure 4. It is similar to the one used in previous work [44], grid stretching is applied outside the jet near-field (see meshes sizes details in section 3.3) in order to damp the acoustic waves and avoid their reflections on the boundary conditions. Note that the flow inside the nozzle is computed in the simulations, including the nozzle convergent.

Figure 4. Computational domain

The CFD simulations are performed with the elsA software [72]. The choice of the numerical settings is guided by best practices based on previous works and features available for unstructured grids in the software. The spatial discretization is 2nd order accurate and relies on a 1-exact flux reconstruction at cell interfaces. The fluxes are computed with a 2nd order Roe scheme. The gradients are computed with a Green-Gauss approach. The time integration is performed with a 2nd order accurate implicit backward differencing scheme with a timestep of 1 μ s and 5 inner sub-iterations per timestep to ensure a decrease of at least 1 order of magnitude of the residuals during the sub-iteration process.

The turbulence modelling approach used is the Zonal Detached Eddy Simulation (ZDES) [42] which combines ZDES mode 3 [40] [43] to achieve a Wall Modelled LES resolution in the nozzle boundary layer and ZDES mode 2 (2020) [73] to achieve a LES resolution in the jet and a RANS modelling everywhere else as depicted in Figure 5. In particular, the turbulence generation in the nozzle boundary layer is performed using tripping dots included in the computational domain using Immersed Boundary Conditions (IBC) as illustrated in Figure 5. The efficiency of this method to quickly develop three-dimensional turbulence without generating spurious noise (a common limitation of synthetic turbulence generators which can be used as an alternative to the present method) is demonstrated in [40] [44], where a detailed discussion on the choice of the tripping dots parameters can be found. In the present case, the height of the tripping dots is equal to 0.6 times the local boundary layer thickness as suggested in [40].

Figure 5. ZDES modes definition and illustration of the IBC trips to trigger turbulent transition inside the nozzle

Isolated jet simulations are first run for 300 D/U_j (with U_j the jet exhaust velocity) to flush out the initial transient, after what flow statistics and data extraction for the far-field noise post-processing are computed for 300 D/U_j to investigate grid convergence. As a matter of fact, the investigations carried out in Sections 4.6 and 4.7.2 show that the choice of 300 D/U_j is acceptable insofar as the data is azimuthally averaged. For the installed jet, where data cannot be azimuthally averaged, post-transient jet flow simulation is extended to 600 D/U_j to reach statistical convergence.

3.3 Meshes

In order to improve the accuracy of the simulations, especially at high frequencies, the present simulations make use of unstructured grids to cluster the grid points in the jet shear layer near the nozzle exit where acoustic sources responsible for high frequency noise are generated. Besides, previous work [44] [50] showed the limitations of the structured grid approach for complex configurations for which unstructured grids are better suited. Of interest, this type of mesh relies on prisms and hexahedra near the wall, and pyramids and tetrahedra everywhere else as illustrated in Figure 6. To the best of the Authors' knowledge, the present work is the first time such meshes have been used to predict jet noise with the elsA software.

Figure 6. Visualizations of the unstructured mesh topology. Blue: prisms and hexahedra, yellow: pyramids, red: tetrahedra

First, the focus is put on the tuning of the mesh inside the nozzle to correctly reproduce the nozzle turbulent boundary layer. Indeed, it was shown in various papers that the state of the nozzle exit boundary layer is key to jet noise generation mechanisms [37] [44] [74] [75] [76]. Therefore preliminary simulations are carried out with a coarse mesh in the jet to ensure that the turbulence modelling methodology derived for structured grids in [44] and illustrated in Figure 5 could be used with unstructured ones as well. Eventually, a wall mesh resolution of $\Delta x^+ = r\Delta\theta^+ = 200$ is found to provide a fair agreement with experimental data (see section 4.2). Note that this resolution is larger than the recommended values for ZDES mode 3 to reach accurate friction coefficient values on a flat plate, but is found sufficient for the purposes of initiating the jet flow development in [44].

The mesh inside the nozzle is then kept constant for all the simulations, while the mesh density in the jet development area is investigated. The decoupling of the mesh densities in various areas of the computational domain is indeed one advantage of the unstructured grid approach. Using basic a priori knowledge of an isolated subsonic jet properties, the jet flow is decomposed into three areas depicted in Figure 7: the shear layer development (in red), up to $x/D=6$, the jet plume mixing area from $x/D=6$ to $x/D=15$ and the acoustic propagation area enclosing the expected acoustic sources up to $x/D=30D$. These three areas are designed to parametrize the mesh sizes depending on the local flow physics and easily generate meshes of increasing density with only a few control parameters.

Figure 7. Mesh refinement areas

In Figure 7, Δ_1 , Δ_2 and Δ_3 are the target edge sizes used to generate the mesh with the Pointwise software (target edge size is Δ_3 in the acoustic propagation area). The metrics generally used to

characterize the size of tetrahedral cells for CFD is the diameter of the inscribed sphere inside the cell.

Three meshes are created to assess the mesh sensitivity of the results. The cells sizes for these meshes are given in Table 1 along with the theoretical maximal Strouhal number which can be reached assuming 15 points per acoustic wavelength.

The rationale for the meshes generation is the following. A first mesh of moderate size, named “Uns-1”, is created using lessons learnt from the literature and previous simulations with structured grids. The same mesh distribution and cell sizes were used to generate the installed jet mesh. Both isolated and installed jet meshes are illustrated in Figure 8 and Figure 9. The mesh density was then increased in order to perform a mesh sensitivity study for the isolated jet. The second mesh, “Uns-2”, is derived by reducing the cell size of 20% at the nozzle lip and potential core and 30% everywhere else, resulting in a total grid count twice as large as the one of “Uns-1”. Finally, mesh “Uns-3” refinement focuses on the acoustic propagation area (in green in Figure 7) with a reduction of 20% of the cell size compared to mesh Uns-2 in this area. Results from simulations on meshes Uns-1 and Uns-2 lead to shorten the refined area at $x/D=27$ in this mesh to save some computational cost. The cell size is also reduced in the potential core in Uns-3 to assess the sensitivity of the results to this parameter.

Mesh name	Computed sizes - diameter of inscribed sphere						Mesh count ($/10^6$)				
	Δ_1/D	Δ_2/D	Δ_3/D	$St_{max}(\Delta_1)$	$St_{max}(\Delta_2)$	$St_{max}(\Delta_3)$	Nozzle inlet	BL	Shear layer	Plume + farfield	Total
Uns-1	0.0021	0.015	0.027	36.0	4.9	2.8	5.5	9.3	19.2	39.8	73.8
Uns-2	0.0016	0.011	0.019	45.0	7.0	4.0	5.5	9.3	41.3	87.6	143.7
Uns-3	0.0016	0.011	0.015	45.0	7.0	4.8	11.4	9.3	41.3	119.5	181.5

Table 1. Mesh sizes (see definition of mesh refinement areas in Figure 5)

The cell sizes distribution in the jet plume can be observed in Figure 8 and Figure 9 for the first mesh used (Uns-1). More quantitatively, the cell sizes are plotted in Figure 10 in order to assess the differences between each mesh.

Of interest, the grid point distribution and grid sizes of structured grids used in previous studies [44] are also plotted in Figure 10 as references. Grid “Struct-Grid1BL” has 54.10^6 cells, and “Struct-Grid2BL” has 156.10^6 cells. These grids provide a radial discretization in the shear layer of around $\Delta r/\delta_{\omega 0} \sim 50$ (where $\delta_{\omega 0}$ is the initial shear layer vorticity thickness). It is noteworthy that due to total grid count limitations, the streamwise grid spacing for the structured grids is much larger than the one obtained with unstructured grids. The azimuthal resolution near the nozzle exit is also improved with unstructured grids as expected. Indeed, the equivalent grid points number near the nozzle exit is 1500 for mesh Uns-1 and 2000 for mesh Uns-2 and Uns-3 instead of 500 for the structured grid Grid2BL. It is noteworthy that several techniques can be used to try and refine locally structured grids, such as partially matching block joins, fully non conformal block interfaces or overset grids. However, in the framework of scale-resolving simulations, these approaches can induce a low-pass filtering of the solution which would be detrimental. Special care must be taken to ensure a continuity of the grid density on both sides of the blocks interfaces, which reduces the efficiency of these approaches in reducing the total grid count. Regarding the overset approach, this aspect is addressed in [77] [78]. Without the use of such specific refinement techniques, one can estimate that the size of a structured grid with a grid density in the jet area in the radial, streamwise and azimuthal directions similar to the ones of mesh Uns-3 would be much more than 1 billion points due to the constraints of the structured grid approach where local grid refinements propagate throughout the computational domain.

Figure 8. Illustration of mesh sizes for isolated and installed jet mesh "Uns-1"

Figure 9. Illustration of mesh sizes in transverse planes for isolated and installed jet mesh "Uns-1"

Figure 10. Mesh sizes along the lipline (left) and jet centerline (right)

4 Validation of the numerical approach for an isolated jet

In the present section, the results of the simulations performed with the unstructured meshes (simulations with mesh "Uns-N" (N=1,2,3) are named "ZDES3 MeshN") are compared with experimental data and the simulation data of Brès et al. [37], labelled as "WMLES Brès et al. (16M)". For the aerodynamic part, the results of the simulation performed with a structured grid of $156 \cdot 10^6$

cells are also included in order to illustrate the improvements achieved. Details for the simulation with the structured grid, named “ZDES3 Grid 2 (elsA-S)” in the following, can be found in [44]. It is noteworthy that this simulation was run with the same turbulence modelling approach (ZDES mode 3 in the nozzle and ZDES mode 2 everywhere else) and the same time integration scheme as the simulations with the unstructured grids but with a different spatial discretization scheme, namely a modified AUSM+P spatial scheme [79].

4.1 Flow visualizations

Snapshots of the simulations are shown in Figure 11. The contours of vorticity emphasize the size as well as the strength of the resolved turbulent structures, and the density gradient in the background characterizes the acoustic waves propagation. When the unstructured mesh density increases, some smaller scales seem to be captured in the aft part of the jet, around 6-8 D. However, even smaller eddies are resolved with the structured grid, which is partly attributed to the low dissipation spatial scheme used. One can also note that the propagation of acoustic waves inside the nozzle is more visible in the structured grid simulation. This is attributed to the small streamwise grid spacing in this area inherited from the boundary layer discretization in the structured grid, which is not the case with the unstructured meshes. The increased mesh density in the nozzle centerline for mesh Uns-3 (see Figure 10) seems to slightly improve this aspect.

Figure 11. Snapshots of mean vorticity (colors) and density gradient (grayscale)

4.2 Nozzle exit boundary layer

Prior to analyzing the jet flow development in the simulations, the nozzle boundary layer evolution is first investigated. A turbulent boundary layer is developed downstream of the tripping dots described in section 2.2 (see also a detailed analysis in [44]). The nozzle exit boundary layer profiles are plotted in Figure 12. The unstructured grid simulations results are in close agreement with the structured grid simulation. The experimental mean and RMS streamwise velocity profiles are fairly well reproduced and the data is close to the reference simulation of Brès et al. [37] Although the agreement is not perfect, the boundary layer obtained in the simulations is arguably representative of the experimental one in terms of thickness and three-dimensional resolved turbulence, which is conjectured to be sufficient in the frame of the present study since the objective is to initiate the jet flow development with a fully turbulent boundary layer as in the experiments.

Figure 12. Nozzle exit boundary layer profiles (azimuthally averaged). The horizontal dashed line on the right hand side plots represents the location of the RANS/LES interface used for the ZDES mode 3 modelling.

4.3 Shear layer development

In order to assess the development of the shear layer downstream of the nozzle exit, profiles along the lipline $r/D=0.5$ are plotted in Figure 13. The slope of the mean velocity decay is well reproduced by all simulations with unstructured meshes, with a slightly even better agreement for ZDES3 Mesh2 and ZDES3 Mesh3 which provide virtually the same results. The level of resolved fluctuations is also in good agreement with the experiments, and the mesh sensitivity is also not significant for this quantity.

Figure 13. Mean and RMS streamwise velocity along the jet lipline ($r/D=0.5$) (azimuthally averaged)

The improvement of the unstructured mesh simulations over the structured one is obvious. It is conjectured that the mesh spacing in the streamwise direction was too large compared to the spacing in the other directions in the structured grid due to total grid count limitation (see grid sizes in Figure 10). The inappropriate aspect ratio of the cells appears to impair the overall development of the jet for $0 < x/D < 10$. This appears to result in an underestimation of the RMS velocity in the shear layer and a global imbalance within the simulated jet which do not present the correct decay slopes for $x/D > 10$ for the mean and RMS velocities. In this regard, it is assumed that the smaller size and isotropy of the grid cells of the unstructured grids provide a better discretization of the shear layer.

4.4 Jet flow development

Mean and RMS streamwise velocity profiles along the jet centerline ($r/D=0$) shown in Figure 14 are consistent with the previous comments. All three simulations performed with unstructured meshes are in very good agreement with the reference data. The mesh sensitivity of the results is likely to stem from the total simulation time rather than from a “true” mesh effect since no azimuthal

average can be performed at this location and the second order statistics may not be completely converged with 300 D/U_j as investigated in section 4.6 (see Figure 18).

Figure 14. Mean and RMS velocities along the jet centerline

Again, the simulation methodology using unstructured meshes brings about a significant improvement over our previous results with structured grids which failed to predict the jet potential core length. As explained for the shear layer development in the previous section, this seems to be a consequence of the large aspect ratio cells in the structured grid (elongated in the streamwise direction due to total grid count limitations) which might cause an imbalance between the generation and discretization of large energy producing turbulent structures and small dissipating eddies.

4.5 Near field pressure fluctuations spectra

In the experiments [37], the jet near pressure field is measured with microphones mounted on a so-called “cage array”, which locations are depicted in Figure 15. Pressure spectra at these locations presented in Figure 16 provide first insights on the acoustics predicted by the simulations.

Figure 15. Location of the jet near field probes (red dots, "microphones cage array" in the experiments [37]) and extraction surfaces (S0, S1, S2) for the far-field noise post-processing

In line with the previous sections, the unstructured meshes simulations predict the experimental spectra with a good accuracy up to $St_D=3$ for the most upstream locations and $St_D=1$ for the most downstream one. However, in all cases the energy peak/hump is located at frequencies around $St_D=0.3$. Therefore it seems that most noise sources are fairly well captured by the simulations. Of interest, one can see in Figure 15 that the extraction surface S0 is closer to the jet than the cage array probes, which was done on purpose to mitigate the acoustic waves dissipation by the mesh in order to improve the accuracy of the far-field noise prediction at higher frequencies.

Figure 16. Pressure fluctuations spectra in the jet near-field (azimuthally averaged)

4.6 Statistical convergence of the flow data

A total simulation time of $300 D/U_j$ is typically used in the literature as well as in the previous section for this type of isolated jets, but some papers indicate that this may be insufficient to reach statistical convergence, including the reference paper of Brès et al. [37] for the present test case. For industrial cases, flow averages are often computed over with $100 D/U_j$ time samples due to computational costs. Furthermore, it is common to use an azimuthal average to compensate for the short simulation time, but this is obviously not possible for installed cases.

Therefore, the simulation with the mesh “Uns-3” was run for a total of $2100 D/U_j$ in order to assess the convergence of the computation of the flow statistics and spectra and provide some insights on the best practices required for the simulation of installed cases. The results presented in this section involve both the influence of the cumulated total simulation time from $100 D/U_j$ up to $2100 D/U_j$ and the results obtained for samples of $100 D/U_j$ and $300 D/U_j$ in order to assess the repeatability of the results when using such short time samples for the computation of the flow statistics.

The influence of the total simulation time and azimuthal average on the shear layer development is evidenced in Figure 17. The azimuthally averaged profiles are almost converged with $100 D/U_j$, with only small variations among the $100 D/U_j$ samples for $x/D > 15$. On the other hand, the raw profiles in the $z=0$ plane shown on the right hand side of Figure 17 display more significant discrepancies between the $100 D/U_j$ and even $300 D/U_j$ samples at all streamwise locations, and it seems that a total simulation time of at least $600 D/U_j$ is necessary to reach consistent results.

Figure 17. Profiles of mean and RMS streamwise velocity along the jet lipline ($r/D=0.5$). Left: with azimuthal averaging, right: no azimuthal averaging

The profiles of mean and RMS streamwise velocity along the jet axis plotted in Figure 18 are in line with the previous comments. Of interest, the dispersion of the results obtained with 100 D/U_j and 300 D/U_j samples is quite significant for quantitative comparisons but would not lead to misinterpretation of the simulation results.

Figure 18. Profiles of mean and RMS streamwise velocity along the jet axis

The near-field pressure spectra shown in Figure 19 provide first insights on the influence of the total simulation time on the noise predictions. The dispersion of the results from 300 D/U_j samples at low frequencies ($St < 0.15$) is of the order of 2 dB/St and reaches around 5 dB/St for 100 D/U_j samples, but the spectra seem to collapse for $T \geq 600 D/U_j$. However, when azimuthally averaged (left part of the figures), the results from 300 D/U_j appear fairly well converged.

Figure 19. Pressure fluctuations spectra in the jet near-field

4.7 Noise radiation sensitivity study

The extrapolation of the pressure fluctuations to the observer positions is performed with the FWH integral surface formulation detailed in Section 2.3. Unsteady flow data are stored on the surface every two iterations of the aerodynamic simulation (frequency sampling $f_s = 500,000$ Hz). This limited downsampling, together with the second order time scheme of the flow simulation, ensure the data stored are not aliased in time. Similarly, the surface grid density is similar to the volume one to avoid spatial aliasing.

The radiation surface needs to be located far enough from the jet to enclose all the noise sources, but the farther the surface the higher the numerical dissipation of the acoustic waves in the CFD simulation before reaching the surface. Hence, its location must be determined very carefully to take into account all the noise sources and to provide the minimum numerical attenuation of the high frequency levels. Three different lateral surfaces, S0, S1, and S2 and two axial extents with endcaps D2 and D3 (see Figure 4 and Figure 15) are considered. For all surfaces considered, pressure levels collapse in the low-frequency range. It indicates that the surfaces are placed correctly and enclose the dominant noise sources. The farther away the surface is from the jet plume, the higher the dissipation of the high frequencies, therefore surface S0-D1-D2 is used in the rest of the analyses of the isolated jet.

4.7.1 CFD grid density

Figure 20. Simulated far-field pressure levels from different CFD meshes (surface S0-D1-D2).
— ZDES Mesh1, — ZDES Mesh2, — ZDES Mesh3

The density of the aerodynamic numerical grid on noise levels is investigated in Figure 20, where noise radiation results obtained with ZDES Mesh1, Mesh2 and Mesh3 are illustrated. The pressure spectral densities, Figure 20 (a), are very similar up to $St = 2$, the three numerical grids are therefore sufficient to capture the low- and medium-frequency noise of the jet (the differences observed between the different meshes in the low frequency part of the spectra come from the insufficient statistical convergence, as discussed later in Section 4.7.2). For larger frequencies, the pressure levels are lower with Mesh1 whereas Mesh2 and Mesh3 provide similar levels up to the maximum considered frequency, $St = 10$. This observation is in line with the near-field spectra presented in Section 4.5. The identical results obtained with Mesh2 and Mesh3 indicate the grid refinement does not improve the propagation of the acoustic waves up to the storage surface. The most energetic noise levels lying below $St = 1$, the high-frequency numerical dissipation observed with Mesh1 has no significant influence on the integrated levels illustrated in Figure 20 (b), where discrepancies are below 0.4 dB for all observation angles.

4.7.2 Statistical convergence of the levels

This paragraph investigates the statistical convergence of the noise levels. The methodology is similar to the one used in Section 4.6 for the aerodynamic flow fields. Power spectral densities and integrated pressure levels are evaluated for different time length varying from 100 D/U_j to 2100 D/U_j and results are presented without and with azimuthal averaging.

Figure 21. Convergence of the power spectral densities at 30° with the duration of the time signal.
— 100 D/U_j samples, — 300 D/U_j samples, — 600 D/U_j , — 900 D/U_j ,
— 1200 D/U_j , — 1500 D/U_j , — 1800 D/U_j , — 2100 D/U_j

Figure 21 reproduces power spectral densities at 30° observer position without (left) and with (right) azimuthal averaging of the levels. The conclusions are qualitatively the same as for the aerodynamic data. Without azimuthal averaging, 100 D/U_j and 300 D/U_j samples do not provide converged spectra and the dispersion is of about 10 dB and 5 dB, respectively, for all the frequencies considered. These discrepancies vanish when the signal length increases and convergence is reached for 600 D/U_j . Azimuthal averaging improves the convergence of the spectra, in particular for the high frequencies,

but a dispersion of about 5 dB remains visible for low frequencies with 100 D/U_j samples, and of about 2 dB for 300 D/U_j samples. This is a consequence of the stronger azimuthal correlation of the low frequency noise, which reduces the efficiency of the averaging in comparison to the lower correlated, higher frequency levels (see Appendix A). The observations are globally similar for other observation angles, not reproduced here.

Figure 22. Convergence of the integrated pressure levels with the duration of the time signal.

— 100 D/U_j samples, — 300 D/U_j samples, — 600 D/U_j , — 900 D/U_j ,
 — 1200 D/U_j , — 1500 D/U_j , — 1800 D/U_j , — 2100 D/U_j

The axial evolution of the integrated pressure levels is visible in Figure 22. Without azimuthal averaging, the dispersion of the 100 D/U_j samples varies between 1 dB at 90° and 4 dB at 25°. This variation reduces to a maximum of 0.5 dB for 300 D/U_j samples, except for the 6th sample (1500 $D/U_j \leq T \leq 1800 D/U_j$) in the downstream arc ($x/D \geq 18$) where specific acoustic events lower the levels up to 1 dB. As soon as the statistics are performed over 600 D/U_j , levels are converged up to 0.15 dB in the upstream arc and 0.3 dB in the downstream arc. Azimuthal averaging improves convergence for $x/D < 20$ (observation angle below 35°) but not in the downstream arc, because of the dispersion of the low-frequency, energetic levels of the PSDs observed in Figure 21.

Figure 23. Standard deviation of the OASPL along the azimuthal direction.

— 100 D/U_j samples, — 300 D/U_j samples, — 600 D/U_j , — 900 D/U_j ,
 — 1200 D/U_j , — 1500 D/U_j , — 1800 D/U_j , — 2100 D/U_j

To conclude these investigations, the standard deviation of the OASPL along the azimuth is illustrated in Figure 23 for each axial position of the microphone antenna. In agreement with previous observations, the standard deviation slowly decreases as the length of the time signals increase. It globally varies up to 0.9 dB for 100 D/U_j samples, between 0.2 and 0.3 dB for 300 D/U_j samples, reduces to circa 0.15 dB for 600 D/U_j and is below 0.1 dB for 2100 D/U_j .

4.8 Acoustic assessment of the simulation

To end with the isolated jet, in this section the simulated results obtained with ZDES Mesh 3, 2100 D/U_j time length and azimuthal averaging are compared with the simulation of Brès et al. [37] and experimental data.

Simulated and experimental power spectral densities are reproduced in Figure 24. Brès et al. assume the limit frequency of their simulation is $St \sim 2$. Above this frequency simulated levels depart from the experimental ones and particularly exhibit a strong overestimation for the low observation angles, below 30° , whereas below $St = 2$ the agreement with the experiments lies within 0.5 dB.

In the present simulation ZDES3 Mesh3, computed levels qualitatively recover the shape of the experimental spectra for all observer angles displayed. The higher grid density (181×10^6 elements) shifts the limit frequency to a much higher value and the agreement with the experiments remains within 5 dB for the maximum experimental frequency available, $St = 8$. More quantitatively, the low-frequency, most energetic levels are slightly larger than those of Brès et al., for all observer positions. At 30° the agreement with the experiments is very good, but the overestimation of the levels rises with the observation angle. Medium frequency levels ($St \sim 0.2-0.3$) are overpredicted up to 3 dB at 60° , whereas a 2 dB overprediction is observed at 90° for both low and medium frequencies. This overprediction is to be associated with the one observed in the near field, see Section 4.5. It is related with the slight overshoot of the turbulent velocity downstream of the nozzle lip (Figure 13), possibly corresponding to some reminiscent laminar/turbulent transition mechanisms in the early stages of the shear layer (despite the tripping of the nozzle boundary layer) which are known to be efficient noise radiators [28] [29].

Figure 24. Experimental and simulated pressure spectra.
 ● Exp. Pprime, — WMLES Brès et al. (16M), — ZDES3 Mesh3 (T = 2100 D/U_j)

The consequence of the overestimation of the low- and medium-frequency levels in the PSDs is a slight overprediction of the integrated pressure levels, as illustrated in Figure 25. In Figure 25 (a), the simulation recovers the experimental noise directivity. Figure 25 (b) reproduces the integrated level difference between the simulations and the experiments, positive values indicating an overprediction of the simulation. For both simulations, the higher the observation angle the larger the overprediction. For simulation ZDES Mesh 3, this overprediction is caused by the slight overestimation of the low- and medium-frequency levels, and it globally remains below 0.5 dB to 1 dB for most angles.

5 Installed jet configuration

Following the results of the isolated case, the installed jet simulation is performed with the grid Mesh1. This grid density is assumed to be sufficient to capture the main physical phenomena at a reasonable computational cost, in particular the scattering of turbulence by the plate trailing edge, which is important for low frequencies. In addition, the simulation is run for 600 D/U_j to ensure the statistical convergence of the data, which cannot be azimuthally averaged.

5.1 Flow simulation

Instantaneous flow visualizations are shown in Figure 26. The shielding effect above the plate as well as the pressure waves scattering by the plate trailing edge are observed in the simulation of the installed case. No obvious influence of the installation can be seen on the jet flow development, which is expected with this configuration.

Figure 26. Flow visualizations. Left: isolated case, right: installed case

The velocity profiles along the jet centerline plotted in Figure 27 confirm that the jet flow development is not modified by the presence of the plate. The isolated and installed case simulations are in good agreement with each other and the experimental data for the isolated case [37] (which are assumed to be valid for the installed case as well).

Figure 27. Mean and RMS of streamwise velocity along the jet centerline ($r/D=0$)

The radial profiles of the mean and RMS velocity (Figure 28 and Figure 29) show that the jet shear layer development only slightly modified in the plate wake (profiles at $x/D=1, 5$ and 10 for $0.5 < r/D < 1$).

Figure 28. Radial profiles of streamwise velocity

Figure 29. Radial profiles of RMS of streamwise velocity

The installation effect on the jet near-field pressure fluctuations is investigated in Figure 30. At $x/D = 0.12$, the shielding leads to a strong reduction of medium- and high-frequency levels above the

plate and strengthens the low-frequency content. This low-frequency rise is also observed for the other azimuthal positions. At $x/D = 2$, the influence of the plate is essentially limited to the shielded observer with a 10 dB reduction compared to the isolated configuration, whereas low frequency levels increase below the wing (unshielded position). For inboard and outboard azimuthal positions, the results are very close to the simulations and the measurements of the isolated case. As the observer location moves downstream ($x/D > 4$), levels start to collapse between installed and isolated jets.

Figure 30. Pressure spectra in the jet near-field.

Shielded position is $\Phi = 90^\circ$; unshielded position is $\Phi = 270^\circ$; inboard/outboard position are $\Phi = 0^\circ/180^\circ$

5.2 Radiated noise

5.2.1 Modeling of noise radiation

Compared to the isolated jet, the presence of the flat plate impact the radiated noise in two different ways. First, due to the coupling between the jet and the plate turbulence is scattered by the trailing edge and generates additional noise [7] [15]. Second, the flat plate reflects the pressure waves and act as a shielding. The classical methodology to compute such a configuration is to solve the propagation of the acoustic waves around the plate in the CFD simulation, the coupling with an integral method being performed outside of the jet-plate region in the uniform, free-field flow [6] [52] [53] [54] [55] [56] [57] [58]. Such an approach may however be very expensive, in particular when the extent of the plate is large. Here, a low-cost alternative method is proposed. In order to limit the computational time, sound propagation around the flat plate is neither included in the CFD simulation (except in the very close vicinity of the jet) nor accounted for through a CFD-CAA coupling, but modelled during the radiation process. Pressure time signals are reconstructed in a two-step simulation from the unsteady flow fields stored on a porous surface surrounding the jet. The direct radiation from the jet to the microphones is performed in a first step using the FWH formulation. The acoustic scattering by the part of the flat plate enclosed in the porous surface is computed by the CFD simulation and is therefore included in this step of the radiation process. Acoustic contributions on the flat plate outside of the porous surface are modelled in a second step: the pressure, its gradient and its time derivative are computed on the plate using the FWH integral formulation and

reflections and shadow effects of the flat plate outside of the porous surface on the radiated noise are modelled as presented in Section 2.3

Figure 31. Porous and reflecting surfaces used for noise radiation.

An illustration of the porous and reflecting surfaces used in the study is visible in Figure 31. The porous surface is adapted from that of the isolated jet configuration to fit the contour of the plate and to include only the jet and the vicinity of the plate trailing edge. The acoustic scattering by the flat plate is therefore computed by the CFD simulation and is included in the first step of the radiation process.

5.2.2 Sensitivity study

Figure 32. Position of the near-field sensors (porous surface S2-D1-D2 is in black)

The accuracy of the radiated noise is ensured by a sensitivity study similar to that of the isolated jet, for sensors on the azimuthal antenna as well as near-field sensors illustrated in Figure 32. In the presence of the plate, the lateral surfaces S0 is particularly found to be too close from the jet and underestimates the levels for $St < 0.3$ for locations upstream of the trailing edge. This underestimation reduces as the surface is farther away from the jet and levels are globally converged for surface S2. It is assumed surface S0 is too tight to include all the additional noise sources associated with turbulence scattering at the trailing edge. In the downstream end, pressure levels are found to be independent of the axial extent of the surface and the surface S2-D1-D2 is used for all the analyses below. From the isolated jet results, noise is expected to be accurate up to $St = 1$.

Figure 33. Influence of the discretization of the flat plate on near-field radiated pressure.

— plate discretization $\lambda_{min}/10$, double layer thickness $\lambda_{min}/100$; — plate discretization $\lambda_{min}/5$, double layer thickness $\lambda_{min}/100$; — plate discretization $\lambda_{min}/10$, double layer thickness $\lambda_{min}/50$

In addition to the surface position, for the installed case two additional parameters need to be evaluated during the radiation process, namely (i) the spatial discretization of the reflecting surface and (ii) the double layer thickness of the surface, used to determine the pressure gradient. For both parameters, discretization is based on the acoustic wavelength λ_{min} of the highest resolved frequency ($St_{max} = 1$). Two discretizations of the plate are considered, with edge sizes of the elements being $\lambda_{min}/5$ and $\lambda_{min}/10$. Both simulations collapse for low- and medium-frequency levels, but spurious high-frequency broadband noise is observed for $St \geq 4$ with the discretization $\lambda_{min}/5$, see Figure 33. This frequency being far above the maximum resolved frequency in the aerodynamic simulation, these discretizations are considered to be sufficient in the present study. For the evaluation of the pressure gradient, double layer thicknesses of $\lambda_{min}/50$ and $\lambda_{min}/100$ are used and no significant difference is observed. In the following, a plate discretization of $\lambda_{min}/10$ and double layer thickness of $\lambda_{min}/100$ are used for all simulations.

5.2.3 Near-field noise radiation

The next step in the validation of the radiation methodology is to compare the pressure radiated on the near-field sensors of Figure 32 with the pressure data directly extracted from the CFD simulation, and which include all the sound production and propagation effects from the mean flow and the solid surfaces. This analysis also makes possible quantifying the contribution of acoustic reflections on the plate to the total pressure. Indeed, the radiation methodology separates the direct radiation from the porous surface to the sensors, labelled as *direct contribution* hereafter, to that of the acoustic reflections on the solid surface, labelled as *reflected contribution*. When the porous surface is designed to include only the noise sources (from the turbulent jet and turbulence scattering by the trailing edge) and not the acoustic reflections on the solid surfaces outside the jet, as done here, both contributions are distinct.

Figure 34. Pressure PSDs on the shielded near-field sensors.

— CFD; — radiated, direct contribution; — radiated, reflected contribution, - - radiated, total contribution

The simulated and radiated (total contribution) pressure spectra on the shielded (above the plate) sensors are illustrated in Figure 34. Globally, both spectra collapse for low frequencies, which validates the radiation methodology. One may however notice a slight underestimation of the radiated levels for the low frequencies for the most upstream sensors, which vanishes for $x/D \geq 2$. The spectra agree up to $St \sim 0.8$, above which CFD levels fall rapidly because of the numerical dissipation. It is worth noting the plateau visible for the radiated pressure above $St \sim 5$ must be disregarded as it is a numerical artefact caused by the insufficient discretization of the surface for such frequencies, see Section 5.2.2.

For sensors NF_S3 and NF_S4, located downstream of the trailing edge, reflections on the flat plate do not significantly contribute to the total pressure levels. Reflections get all the more important as the sensor is moved far upstream of the trailing edge. They essentially occur for low frequencies and need to be accounted for to recover the CFD levels, as they exhibit levels similar to those of the direct radiation. For sensors NF_S2, direct contribution for instance underestimates the CFD levels by 4 dB, and this underestimation rises to 8 dB for sensor NF_S1.

Figure 35. Pressure PSDs on the unshielded near-field sensors.

— CFD; — radiated, direct contribution; — radiated, reflected contribution, - - radiated, total contribution

The previous observations for the shielded sensors also apply for the unshielded sensors visible in Figure 35. One may simply note that contributions of the reflections for the upstream sensors are lower on the unshielded side compared to the shielded side.

Figure 36. Pressure PSDs on the lateral near-field sensors.

— CFD; — radiated, direct contribution; — radiated, reflected contribution, - - radiated, total contribution

To end the validation, pressure spectra are reproduced in Figure 36 for lateral sensors below the plate, one diameter downstream of the nozzle exit. Again, the radiated spectra collapse with the CFD data in the low frequency range. There is no specific grid refinement to capture the acoustic waves as they propagate away from the jet axis in CFD, so that numerical dissipation is large and pressure levels rapidly drop for medium and high frequencies, whereas those levels are better captured with the integral method. For these sensors, contributions of reflections are as large as or larger than the direct contribution at low frequencies, and only a few dB below the direct contribution in the

medium frequency range, which highlights the role of acoustic reflections on the surface for the pressure levels in this area

5.2.4 Pressure on the azimuthal antenna

Figure 37. Pressure PSDs on the azimuthal antenna, shielded side ($\Phi=80^\circ$).

● Exp. Pprime; — simulation, direct contribution;
— simulation, reflected contribution, — simulation, total contribution

The accuracy of the installed jet simulation is now addressed through the comparison of the radiated pressure on the azimuthal antenna with the experimental data of Pprime. The pressure spectra above the plate (shielded side, $\Phi=80^\circ$) are reproduced in Figure 37 for four positions of the axial antenna. There are no experimental data available for the observation angle $\theta = 120^\circ$ but jet-plate interaction noise is known to be large at aft angles [8] [13] [15], hence the interest for its analysis. For the first three angles, we observe a good agreement between the simulation and the experimental data up to $St = 1$, the grid cut-off frequency, despite a slight overestimation up to 3 dB of the low frequency levels especially at 30° . The pressure levels are driven by the direct contribution, reflections on the flat plate being always negligible except for the low frequencies ($St \leq 0.1$) at 90° where they become comparable to the direct contribution (it is recalled the high-frequency reflected levels are spurious noise and must not be considered). The predominance of the direct contribution is still observed farther upstream, for $\theta = 120^\circ$, even if pressure levels are now dominated by the reflected contribution below $St = 0.1$.

Figure 38. Pressure PSDs on the azimuthal antenna, unshielded side ($\Phi=260^\circ$).

● Exp. Pprime; — simulation, direct contribution;
 — simulation, reflected contribution, — simulation, total contribution

Pressure levels on the unshielded side ($\Phi=260^\circ$) are visible in Figure 38. Previous conclusions drawn for the shielded side also apply here, with nevertheless a better agreement between the simulation and the experiments at low frequencies for $\theta = 30^\circ$.

Figure 39. Experimental and simulated integrated pressure levels on the azimuthal antenna

Next, cartographies of the integrated pressure levels along the axial and azimuthal directions are reproduced in Figure 39. We recall azimuthal angles $0^\circ \leq \Phi \leq 180^\circ$ correspond to the shielded side ($y \geq 0$) whereas $180^\circ \leq \Phi \leq 360^\circ$ correspond to the unshielded side ($y \leq 0$). First, the geometry being symmetric along the plane $z = 0$, integrated levels are expected to be symmetric with respect to the azimuthal angle $\Phi = 90^\circ$ for the shielded side and $\Phi = 270^\circ$ for the unshielded side. This is indeed the case numerically, which confirms the correct statistical convergence of the levels as expected from isolated jet results, Section 4.7.2. The variations of the integrated levels are correctly captured numerically and the azimuthal variation of the pressure level caused by the plate is accurately reproduced. The highest levels are observed on the shielded side, levels are lower on the unshielded

side and the minimum levels are found near the sideline direction ($\Phi = 20^\circ$ and 160°) for $x/D \leq 10$. More quantitatively, the agreement lies below 0.3 dB for most of the observation angles, except in the downstream arc ($x/D \geq 20$) and in particular on the shielded side where the simulation is up to 1 dB larger than the measurements.

Figure 40. Axial evolution of the integral pressure levels on the shielded ($\Phi = 80^\circ$) and unshielded sides ($\Phi = 260^\circ$) of the azimuthal antenna. ● Exp. Pprime; — simulation, direct contribution; - - simulation, total contribution

The quantitative comparison between the experiments and the simulation is better visible in Figure 40, with the axial evolution of the pressure levels above ($\Phi = 80^\circ$) and below ($\Phi = 260^\circ$) the plate. For $x/D = 25$ ($\theta = 30^\circ$), the level on the shielded side is 1 dB higher than on the unshielded side in the experiments and 1.5 dB in the simulation. In addition to the total radiated noise, the direct contribution is also reproduced in the figure. Direct and total contributions match downstream ($x/D \geq 15$, $\theta \leq 45^\circ$) but slightly differ for lower axial positions, which evidences the contribution of the reflections on the plate to the total noise. The reflected contribution is 7 to 10 dB lower than the direct contribution for these positions and is not reproduced in the figure, but it is sufficient to modulate the direct contribution up to 0.4 dB. Total levels are higher than direct contributions for $x/D \leq 0$, hence constructive interferences between direct and reflected contributions, whereas they are lower for $0 \leq x/D \leq 15$, hence destructive interferences.

Figure 41. Direct and reflected contribution of the simulated noise on the azimuthal antenna

Figure 41 gives the separate contributions of direct and reflected contributions on the azimuthal antenna. Overall, direct contribution is always higher than reflected one. The highest reflected levels are found for $x/D \leq 10$ ($\theta \geq 55^\circ$) on the lateral azimuthal direction, $\Phi \sim 0^\circ$ and 180° , where their contribution on the total levels are expected to be the largest.

Figure 42. Azimuthal evolution of the integral pressure levels for different axial positions of the azimuthal antenna.

● Exp. Pprime; — simulation, direct contribution;
— simulation, reflected contribution, - - simulation, total contribution

This expectation is confirmed with the azimuthal profiles of the integrated levels, visible in Figure 42. Reflected noise has no contribution downstream ($\theta = 30^\circ$) and starts to be visible for $\theta = 60^\circ$. For $\theta = 90^\circ$ and 120° reflections contribute to the total for all azimuthal angles. Their highest contribution is found near $\Phi \sim 0^\circ$ and 180° where the direct contribution is also the lowest, leading to differences between the direct contribution and total level of several dB.

6 Conclusions

This article focuses on the numerical simulation of jet noise installation effects through the coupling of an advanced Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) method for prediction of the noise sources and an integral formulation to reconstruct the time pressure histories at microphones positions. The case considered is an isothermal single stream nozzle at Mach number 0.9 and with diameter-based Reynolds number of 10^6 . The turbulent boundary layer inside the nozzle is reproduced through the use of Zonal Detached Eddy Simulations mode 3 method, which acts as a Wall Modelled Large-Eddy-Simulation, together with the inclusion of roughness elements in the computational domain using Immersed Boundary Conditions to generate turbulence. The numerical grid is unstructured, mainly composed of tetrahedra, to cluster the grid points in the jet shear layer and to get rid of the limitations imposed by structured grid approach.

The numerical approach is first validated for the isolated configuration. The grid convergence is investigated for 3 meshes varying from 73.8×10^6 to 181.5×10^6 elements. It is concluded that a coherent grid densification must be achieved between the source generation and noise propagation areas to be best efficient. Additionally, statistical data are found to be converged for $600 D/U_j$ long time signals, this duration being possibly reduced to $300 D/U_j$ when the data are azimuthally averaged. For the highest grid density, simulated noise levels are globally accurately simulated at least up to $St = 8$, the highest experimental frequency available, and integrated pressure levels collapse within 1 dB with the experiments. The installed configuration is investigated in a second time and builds on the previous conclusions. An innovative noise radiation methodology based on integral methods is proposed to reconstruct the pressure signals at microphone locations with a reduced numerical cost. Noise generation and propagation in the CFD simulation is limited to the jet

plume and jet-plate interaction areas, whereas sound reflections on the plate are modelled during a two-step radiation process. The simulation compares very favorably with the experimental data, azimuthal noise variations induced by the plate are correctly captured and noise levels collapse within 1 dB.

The results presented in this article give confidence in the numerical capability to accurately predict installed jet noise. The simulation process seems mature enough to be used both for industrial assessment of new design and in prospective research studies in conjunction with experiments, for instance to derive JSI mitigation strategies. A potential bottleneck for the application of the noise radiation method is the important surface storage, required to reach statistical convergence, and all the more important as the target cut-off frequency is large and requires a dense grid. This limitation could be alleviated through the use of an acoustic co-processing where far-field pressure reconstruction is performed on the fly, along with the CFD simulation.

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Appendix A Azimuthal correlation of radiated noise

The correlation coefficients along the azimuthal direction of the time histories of pressure radiated on the azimuthal array are computed in this appendix for the isolated jet. For two time signals $s_1(t)$ and $s_2(t)$, the correlation coefficient c_{s_1,s_2} writes

$$c_{s_1,s_2} = \frac{\sigma_{s_1,s_2}}{\sigma_{s_1}\sigma_{s_2}}$$

with σ_{s_1,s_2} the covariance

$$\sigma_{s_1,s_2} = \overline{(s_1(t) - \overline{s_1(t)})(s_2(t) - \overline{s_2(t)})}$$

σ_s the standard deviation

$$\sigma_s = \sqrt{\sigma_{s,s}}$$

and where $\overline{(\cdot)}$ corresponds to time averaging. To investigate the variation of the correlation with the frequency bandwidth, a low-pass, bass-band or high-pass filter is first applied to the time signals prior to computing the correlation coefficients. This filtering is performed in the frequency domain (non-causal filtering). First, the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) of the time signals are computed; second, all coefficients outside the bandwidth of interest are nullified; third, time signals are reconstructed using an Inverse FFT (IFFT). The four filters considered are summarized in Table 2.

	Stmin	Stmax
Full signal	-	-
Low-pass filter signal	0.05	0.1
Band-pass filter signal	0.1	1.0
High-pass filter signal	1.0	10.0

Table 2. Frequency bandwidths considered for the frequency filtering of the pressure signal

The analysis is performed with $2100 D/U_j$ long time signals and the correlation coefficient is computed for each axial position of the azimuthal antenna. The azimuthal evolution of the correlation coefficient is reproduced in Figure 43 for four axial positions and the four frequency filtering mentioned above.

Figure 43. Azimuthal evolution of the correlation coefficient for the radiated pressure.

— — full signals; — low-pass filter signals; — band-pass filter signals; — high-pass filter signals

For the full signal, the azimuthal correlation is very large for the low observation angles and reduces as the observation angle grows. At 20° , the minimum correlation coefficient is 0.7 for the maximum angular distance $\Delta\Phi = 180^\circ$. A correlation of 0.6 is observed for $\Delta\Phi = 60^\circ$ at 30° , whereas the angular distance drops below $\Delta\Phi = 20^\circ$ at 60° and 90° for the same correlation level. For these two latter observation angles of 60° and 90° , the correlation rapidly falls to zero for larger angular distances.

Considering the filtered signals, the evolution of the correlation coefficient is qualitatively similar for the four observation angles reproduced. The largest correlations are observed for the low-pass filtered signals, and the correlation levels decay as the frequency bandwidth considered grows. Generally speaking, correlations levels are always higher for low observation angles (20° and 30°) and decrease as the observation angle rises (60° and 90°).